

Marginal lands for Growing Industrial Crops

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Type

R Document, report

DEM Demonstrator, pilot, prototype

DEC Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.

OTHER

Dissemination Level

PU Public

CO Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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1 Publishable executive summary

The MAGIC project aims to promote the sustainable development of efficient and beneficial industrial crops on marginal lands. A database and a crop support system have been developed, including detailed agricultural information to be of great use to farmers.

In addition, marginal lands in Europe have also been analysed and several optimal crops have been proposed, with the aim of developing sustainable best practice options for industrial crops. The impact of MAGIC will be maximised by integrating the sustainability aspects (encompassing environment, society, and economy) of value chains.

Work Package 8 - Dissemination and link establishment with EIP AGRI, seeks to propagate the project results, database, maps and DSS tool in order to enhance farmers' knowledge, plus creating strong links with EIP AGRI.

Therefore, MAGIC's network efforts were necessary in order to achieve and validate the established goals through a multi-actor approach. This deliverable aims to present the interaction held between MAGIC project partners and the COPA-COGECA, the organisation that represents farmers and cooperatives at European level.

In this sense, several interactions were held to update COPA-COGECA's related Working Groups (WGs) about the expected outcomes and the final results from the project. In addition, the involvement of Spanish Co-ops at the EIP-AGRI Subgroup of Innovation (Sol), representing COPA-COGECA, was a useful position to jointly support and update MAGIC activities.

2 Introduction

The MAGIC partners have been reporting all their results to COPA-COGECA throughout the project. These contacts were performed through Spanish Co-ops, a member organisation of COPA-COGECA.

COPA-COGECA is the organisation that looks after the interests of EU farmers and cooperatives. Hence, the Committee of Professional Agricultural Organisations (COPA) and the General Confederation of Agricultural Cooperatives (COGECA) are coordinated to solve challenges postured by European decision-makers. It permits European farmers and cooperatives to voice their thoughts and suggestions on agricultural matters, regardless of their agricultural activity.

COPA represents European farmers in order to support the greatest interests of the agricultural sector among the EU institutions and other significant actors. It seeks the development of useful policy and strategic projects that raise consciousness of the multifunctional role of farms. It operates as a platform for exchanges where solutions to any technical or commercial obstacles within the EU and beyond. It promotes the communication and diffusion of the European farmers opinions´.

COGECA pursues to represent all the interests of European agri-food, forestry, and fisheries cooperatives in the context of the EU institutions and other socio-economic organisations contributing to European decision-making. It strengthens the network of European agricultural cooperatives and promotes their enterprise collaboration. It enables the exchange of most excellent practices and creates platforms for dialogue on strategic corporate progress to find suitable solutions to existing and future conflicts and to seize emerging opportunities. It promotes and presents ground-breaking resolutions to produce additional value for the benefit of farmers, people, the natural environment, and customers.

Some challenges that this organisation faces are improving the production and use of renewable energy on-farm, searching new opportunities and tackling barriers. Ensuring a decent standard of living for European farmers, maintaining the family farming model. Lower GHG and NH₃ emissions, boosting carbon storage and sequestration. Rise yield in terms of climate change adaptation and mitigation.

COPA-COGECA is dedicated to creating new effective policies and strategies, in order to: raise consciousness of the farms multifunctionality, endorse fair incomes for farmers, encourage the entrepreneurial cooperation of European cooperatives, promote ideas to benefit farmers, society, environment and consumers.

Also, it is worth mentioning that MAGIC partners have been involved in many events in order to disseminate the actions and results to cooperatives and farmers. Within these workshops, there were participants and attendees such as European Innovation Partnership for Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI), the European Network for Rural Development (ENRD) and the European Commission (EC).

3 Interaction with COPA-COGECA's Working Groups

The interactions between MAGIC project and COPA-COGECA have been mainly based on the exchange of updated and relevant information on industrial crops performance over marginal lands. Initially, main targeted COPA-COGECA's working groups (WGs) were (i) Research and Innovation, (ii) Oilseeds and Protein Crops, (iii) Cereals, (iv) Environment, (v) Bioenergy and (vi) Rural Development. However, as the project evolved, many other COPA-COGECA's WGs such as bioenergy, biotechnology, tobacco, flowers and plants, starch, flax and hemp, seeds, sugar, hops, dried fodder and cotton were also approached by MAGIC partners (see *Figure 1*).

To the attention of the members of the Working Parties on Environment, Research and Innovation, Bioenergy, Biotechnology and Non-Food, Tobacco, Flowers and Plants, Starch, Cereals, Flax and Hemp, Oilseeds and Protein Crops, Seeds, Sugar, Hops, Dried Fodder and Cotton
CC: National Offices

Dear Members,

On behalf Cooperativas Agro Alimentarias, you are invited to the final event of the [H2020 MAGIC project](#), which will take place on the **2nd December from 8:30 to 16:50**.

The MAGIC project aims to promote the sustainable development of industrial crops on marginal, profitable and resource-efficient land. To achieve this, [a database has been set up](#) (still in progress) with these crops, including agronomic characteristics, required inputs, yield evolution and quality levels according to the final application. In parallel, [lands in Europe with adverse natural conditions are being mapped](#) and characterised in order to provide a spatial classification that will serve as a basis for the development of best sustainable practices for industrial crops. A [decision support system](#) is also in development, based on both crops and MAGIC maps, validated by the participation of farmers and users to select the most promising industrial crops for Europe. It involves 26 partners from 12 countries and is led by [CRES](#).

You can find the agenda here: [RES\(21\)7710 \(rev.1\)](#)
Link to register [here](#)

Kind regards,

Figure 1. COPA-COGECA invitation to MAGIC final event. *Source: Spanish Co-ops, 2021.*

At the beginning of the project, several contacts with COPA-COGECA's WGs were performed on a face-to-face mode (as initially planned), through presential presentations in COPA-COGECA's headquarters (Brussels). However, due to COVID-19 pandemic restrictions, the dynamics of the events had to be switched to an online format in the form of webinars.

The first physical presentation of the MAGIC project to COPA-COGECA's WGs took place on September 23, 2019. This meeting was convened in Brussels (Belgium), at COPA-COGECA's premises. Taking advantage of the presence of more than 20 COPA-COGECA's members at a Research and Innovation (R&I) WG periodical meeting, Spanish Co-ops staff requested to include a specific item (see *Figure 2*) in the agenda titled "Alternative crops for bioeconomy: MAGIC and PANACEA". The participants were originally from several EU countries, including Austria, Belgium, Finland, Germany, Italy, Lithuania, Netherlands, Sweden, Spain, and United Kingdom. MAGIC and PANACEA projects were presented jointly due to their similarities.

RES(19)7310:1 – TC/fb

TO:	Members of the Copa-Cogeca <i>ad hoc</i> Working Party on Research and Innovation
COPY:	National offices
FROM:	Tobia Capuzzo
PAGES:	2
DATE:	28 th August 2019

Re: Invitation to the meeting of the Copa-Cogeca *ad hoc* Working Party on Research and Innovation on 23rd September 2019

Dear Sir or Madam,

On behalf of the Chair, **Mr Daniele Rossi**, we have the pleasure of inviting you to attend the meeting of the *ad hoc* Working Party on Research and Innovation (RES) which will be held on

23rd September 2019 from 14.00 p.m. to 6:00 p.m
at the Copa-Cogeca Secretariat
61 rue de Trèves, 1040 Brussels

Please pass this message on to any colleagues who may be interested and register for the meeting via [this link](#) before 16th September 2019.

Please regularly check the Research section on Agri Info for the latest available documents and to consult the documents you will need for the meeting.

Yours faithfully,

Tobia Capuzzo

Draft Agenda

1. Adoption of the draft agenda [RES\(19\)7310 \(rev.1\)](#)
2. Approval of the minutes of the previous meeting [RES\(19\)2255 \(rev.1\)](#)
3. Exchange of views on Horizon Europe programme; state of play, next steps and the mission on "healthy soils and the food system". [RES\(19\)7330 \(rev.1\)](#)
4. Exchange of views on S3 priorities of the Smart Specialization Platform. [RES\(19\)7331 \(rev.1\)](#)
5. Discussion with the members on the R&I priorities for 2020. [RES\(19\)7332 \(rev.1\)](#)
6. **Presentations** and updates on
 - a. Alternative crops for bio-economy: MAGIC and PANACEA
 - b. FARMDEMO, PLAID, AGRIDEMO and NEFERTITI
 - c. FIELDS
 - d. LIFE GALIA *sense*
7. Update on H2020 projects and calls.
 - a. [Innoseta](#)
 - b. [Smartchain](#)
 - c. [Disarm](#)
 - d. [SmartAgriHubs](#)
8. Presentation of the Research and Innovation Days 2019
9. AOB

Figure 2. Research and Innovation WG meeting agenda. *Source: Spanish Co-ops, 2019.*

The main objective of this meeting (see *Figure 3*) was to present to COPA-COGECA the interests of Spanish Co-ops (as a member organisation) in relation to MAGIC (crop diversification alternatives adapted to Spanish marginal lands and ways of crop management focusing sustainability), as well as the main objectives of the project, the planned activities and the tasks that were already ongoing (such as the identification of EU marginal lands or the creation of a Decision Support System).

Presentation of Magic and Panacea projects in WPresearch COPA-COGECA

ALTERNATIVE CROPS FOR BIOECONOMY

Juan Sagarna. Spanish Agrifood Cooperatives. 23rd September 2019. Brussels

WP2. So far actions ...

WP2.
Mapping of marginal land in M-AEZ

→

	1. Advance diagnostic	2. Executive tool innovation	3. Advance tool innovation	4. Low cost advisory	5. Advance tool innovation	6. Advance tool innovation	7. Advance tool innovation	8. Advance tool innovation
Alpine	80%	22%	0%	2%	45%	47%	61%	39%
Atlantic	4%	18%	1%	1%	12%	2%	20%	7%
Continental	1%	3%	2%	1%	5%	2%	14%	6%
Mediterranean	12%	1%	1%	6%	18%	9%	34%	6%
North	20%	1%	2%	1%	17%	2%	71%	2%
Grand Total	11%	8%	1%	2%	12%	6%	29%	7%

Figure 3. Extract of the presentation held to R&I WG. *Source: Spanish Co-ops, 2019.*

The second presentation to COPA-COGECA's WGs took place one month later, on September 24, 2019, at COPA-COGECA's headquarters (Brussels, Belgium). On this occasion, more than 40 members of the cereals, oilseeds and protein crops WGs were present. Similarly than in the previous meeting, both MAGIC and PANACEA projects were presented jointly due to their similarities and the involvement of Spanish Co-ops as rightful partner in them.

The presentation was executed by Spanish Co-ops staff (see *Figure 4*), stressing how industrial crops could represent a unique opportunity for the cooperatives and their farmers to increase the added value of their productions while cultivating marginal or abandoned lands, in the framework of the bioeconomy.

Figure 4: MAGIC presentation for COPA-COGECA's WGs. *Source: Spanish Co-ops, 2019.*

Despite more physical meetings were planned with specific COPA-COGECA's WGs for 2020, due to the COVID pandemic irruption at the beginning of that year, MAGIC partners were forced to re-shape a new communication strategy in order to be able to transfer MAGIC progress to COPA-COGECA's members. In this sense, Spanish Co-ops joined forces with CRES (MAGIC project coordinator) and Wageningen University (WR) to arrange an online event initially aimed just for the environment, bioenergy, and rural development COPA-COGECA's WGs, but later expanded to other related COPA-COGECA's WGs and also for all interested organisations.

Hence, Spanish Co-ops, in close collaboration with COPA-COGECA's staff, organised a webinar titled "Non-food Crops for European Marginal Areas", where sixteen different (and related) COPA-COGECA's WGs (see *Figure 5*) were invited. A registration link with the event information was also published at Spanish Co-ops and MAGIC websites and social media.

To the attention of the Working Parties on Environment, Research and Innovation, Bioenergy, Biotechnology and Non-Food, Tobacco, Flowers and Plants, Starch, Cereals, Flax and Hemp, Oilseeds and Protein Crops, Seeds, Sugar, Hops, Dried Fodder and Cotton
Cc: National Offices

Dear Members,

On behalf of Cooperativas Agro-alimentarias, we would like to invite you to the webinar titled **Non-Food Crops for European Marginal Areas that will be held virtually on 2nd November between 3-5pm.**

Your participation to the event will be highly welcome, as the webinar aims to address farmers and cooperatives.

The webinar will discuss and disseminate the results of two projects [MAGIC](#) and [PANACEA](#), with invited speakers Ms. Efthymia Alexopoulou, Responsible for Energy Crops Unit in Biomass Department at CRES and Ms. Berien Elbersen, Senior researcher land use and integrated environmental assessment at Wageningen University & Research.
You can find attached the latest version of the agenda ([RES\(20\)7804 \(rev.1\)](#)).
And a link to register for the event [here](#).

Please feel free to share this event within your network.

Kind regards,

Figure 5. COPA-COGECA invitation to MAGIC's event. *Source: Spanish Co-ops, 2020.*

As a result, the third presentation of the MAGIC project to COPA-COGECA took place on November 2, 2020. The presentations were performed by CRES and Wageningen University staff speakers. Spanish Co-ops moderated the event.

The coordinator of the MAGIC and PANACEA projects (CRES) presented the different Work Packages in which both projects were structured, their initial targets and achieved results, including a description of the most promising alternative crops and the available tools developed within both projects. Afterwards, Wageningen University staff presented the huge mapping effort made to identify marginal lands at a very high-resolution level (LAU1) all over Europe (see *Figure 7*).

The attendance rate was considerably high, as approximately fifty assistants participated in the event. Most of the attendants were COPA-COGECA's member organisations from all over Europe (see *Figure 6*) such as farmers and cooperatives representatives, but there were also present members of research entities, policy, SMEs and two participants of Canadian companies.

Country	Attendance
Spain	14
France	5
Greece	5
Italy	4
UK	4
Belgium	3
Netherlands	3
Austria	1
Latvia	1
Lithuania	1
Poland	1
Sweden	1

Figure 6: European attendance to the event. *Source: Spanish Co-ops, 2021.*

MAGIC **PANACEA**

NON-FOOD CROPS FOR EUROPEAN MARGINAL AREAS

Webinar

cooperativas agro-alimentarias España **NOVEMBER 2nd**
3 pm to 5 pm (CET)
English language
*This event will be recorded

PROGRAMME

3:00 pm Welcome and introduction of the event.
Mr. Pablo Fernández, Sustainability, Quality and Innovation Department at Agri-food Cooperatives of Spain.

3:05 pm Contextualisation of MAGIC & PANACEA projects. Presentation of the most promising alternative crops to be introduced in European Areas and the available on-line tools.
Ms. Efthymia Alexopoulou, Responsible for Energy Crops Unit in Biomass Department of CRES and Coordinator of both MAGIC & PANACEA projects.

3:50 pm Time for questions.

4:00 pm Presentation of the MAGIC mapping of European agricultural areas, with great details on segmentation and geopositioning. MAGIC decision support system tool.
Ms. Berien Elbersen, Senior researcher land use and integrated environmental assessment at Wageningen University & Research.

4:45 pm Time for questions.

4:55 pm Acknowledgements and closure of the event.
Mr. Pablo Fernández, Sustainability, Quality and Innovation Department at Agri-food Cooperatives of Spain

SPEAKERS

BERIEN ELBERSEN
WAGENINGEN U&R

EFTHYMIA ALEXOPOULOU
CRES

MODERATOR

PABLO FERNÁNDEZ
COOPERATIVAS ACRO-ALIMENTARIAS ESPAÑA

SIGN UP

These projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N.773501 (PANACEA), N° 727698 (MAGIC).

Figure 7: Programme of MAGIC's event: *Source: Spanish Co-ops, 2020.*

All the presented tools are available over the following links: [PANACEA Platform](#), [MAGIC Decision Support System \(DSS\)](#), [MAGIC Crops](#) and [MAGIC Maps](#).

The meeting was recorded with the consent of all participants and it is also available through the following link:

[Seminario Web: Cultivos no-alimentarios para las zonas marginales europeas - YouTube](#)

Finally, on December 2, 2021, all the COPA-COGECA's WGs involved so far were invited to the final MAGIC event (see *Figure 1*), which took place in Lisbon at the Universidade NOVA de Lisboa in an hybrid mode (presential + online).

4 Other relevant interactions (multiactor networking)

Besides of the interaction held with COPA-COGECA's WGs, MAGIC project's members participated at EU level events and had the chance to interact with related project members taking advantage of Spanish Co-ops network and its presence at the EIP-AGRI Subgroup of Innovation (representing COPA-COGECA).

One of these events was organised by the EIP-AGRI in Vilnius on February 6 and 7, 2019. There, the coordinator of MAGIC and PANACEA projects (CRES), had the chance to summarise the outcomes in an open interview (see *Figure 8*) with the support of FCT-UNL and LAMMC staff.

The poster features a top image of hands holding small green plants in soil. To the right is the EIP-AGRI logo, a stylized sunburst, and the text 'eip-agri AGRICULTURE & INNOVATION'. Below the logo is the text 'funded by' followed by the European Union flag and 'European Commission'.

EIP-AGRI WORKSHOP OPPORTUNITIES FOR FARM DIVERSIFICATION IN THE CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY
6-7 FEBRUARY 2019- VILNIUS, LITHUANIA

PROGRAMME

EIP-AGRI Workshop: Opportunities for farm diversification in the circular bioeconomy
6-7 February 2019
Vilnius, Lithuania

Day 1: Wednesday 6 February 2019

12:00 – 12:30 Welcome lunch - Restaurant Riverside (in the hotel)

12:30 – 13:00 Registration

13:00 – 13:50 Welcome & introduction

- **Ms. Sarah Watson**, *Lead facilitator*. Warm up: who is in the room?
- **Mr. Darius Liutikas**, *Vice-minister - Ministry of Agriculture of Lithuania*. Welcome to Lithuania
- **Mr. Alberto D'Avino**, *European Commission DG AGRI*. Introduction to DG AGRI and EIP-AGRI activities
- Interviews with:
 - **Mr. Paolo Mantovi**, *EIP-AGRI Operational Group representative*
 - **Ms. Efthymia Alexopoulou**, *Researcher*
 - **Mr. James Gaffey**, *BBI project representative*
- Introducing the event programme and the Open Space opportunity, **Ms. Sarah Watson**

13:50 – 14:20 Presentations

- **Mr. Liutauras Guobys**, *European Commission DG RTD*. Introduction to the EU bio-economy strategy,
- **Mr. Jose Ruiz ESPI**, *European Commission DG AGRI*. Feedback on a workshop for policy makers on the integration of primary producers in the bio-economy,
- **Ms. Laura Jalasjoki**, *ENRD Contact Point*. State of play on the ENRD Thematic Group on the bio-economy,

Figure 8: EIP-AGRI planning. *Source: EIP-AGRI, 2019.*

All the information provided at this event can be accessed through [EIP-AGRI website](#), counting with the [list of participants](#) and the [final report](#) that is available for public users.

Moreover, on July 3, 2019, a European Network of Rural Development (ENRD) event took place in Brussels (see *Figure 9*). The session, titled: “Bioeconomy: Seizing the opportunity for rural Europe” counted with the participation of Spanish Co-ops staff and intended to continue the strategy analysis for the advancement of a sustainable and circular bioeconomy in the European Union. More than 200 professionals from several European countries were present, such as farmers, cooperatives, research centres, universities, government agents and staff of the ENRD.

Figure 9: ENRD event picture. *Source: Spanish Co-ops, 2019.*

During the symposium, Spanish Co-ops was asked to disclose the main obstacles for bioeconomy implementation in cooperatives and agroindustry's. It was emphasized the need to encourage and create a solid biomass market and also problems regarding the ambiguity with which the agri-food by-products are contained in the European Waste Catalogue (EWC) were highlighted. The administration considers certain by-products as waste, implying that more complex procedures should be done for their management and/or marketing, ending up preventing their recovery.

Lastly, the requirement to line up the needs of bio-product industries and farmers was also underscored, as their cooperation is necessary to create a lasting relationship between the market and biomass suppliers.

Additionally, an EC workshop was arranged on October 15, 2019 in Brussels (see *Figure 10*). The session titled: “Promoting education, training and skills across the bioeconomy” counted with the participation of Spanish Co-ops staff and intended to support the implementation of action 2.4. of the updated EU Bioeconomy Strategy and Action Plan.

The present experts had expertise of bioeconomy sectors including agriculture & forestry, food systems and bio-based innovation systems. The European Commission services that joined in the workshop were DG AGRI, DG ENV, DG MARE, DG RTD, DG EMPL and JRC.

Spanish Co-ops team communicated and debated all the experiences and barriers that could be overcome through education such as lack of knowledge regarding biomass valorisation alternatives for farmers and agroindustries.

Promoting education, training and skills across the bioeconomy	
<p>15 October 2019, 9:30 – 17:30 ORBN 03/078 & ORBN 03/067 (Session I) ORBN 11th floor (Session II)</p>	
DRAFT AGENDA	
9:30	<p>Welcome and introduction European Commission</p>
9:45-10:45	<p>Session I. Part I. Presentations of the current initiatives and EU funded projects. Preliminary mapping of skill gaps and related educational programmes across bioeconomy. Results from EU funded projects. (UrBiofuture, Askfood, BioEnergyTrain, Blueprint on sectoral cooperation on skills for Bio-economy, new technologies & innovation in agriculture). Q&A</p>
10:45-11:00	<i>Coffee break</i>
11:00-12:00	<p>Session I. Part II. Presentations of the current initiatives and EU funded projects. Industry perspective on the challenges and approaches towards developing skills for bioeconomy (Metsä Group, RethinkResources). The bioeconomy and a future biobased food industry and agriculture sector: How can workers' organisations shape the change? (EFFAT). Lessons learnt and best practices in communication, awareness raising and education for bioeconomy (EuBioNet). Q&A</p>
12:00-13:30	<i>Lunch break</i>
13:30-14:30	<p>Session II. Part I. Interactive discussion (World Café format) Breakout groups' discussion and reporting on key issues identified during the mapping of the current initiatives and EU funded projects in the area of education for bioeconomy.</p>
14:45-15:00	<i>Coffee break</i>
15:00-16:45	<p>Session II. Part II. Interactive discussion (World Café format) Breakout groups' discussion and reporting on key issues identified during the mapping of the current initiatives and EU funded projects in the area of education for bioeconomy.</p>
16:45-17:30	Closing remarks and final discussion

Figure 10: EC Workshop agenda. *Source: Spanish Co-ops, 2019.*

By the other hand, at the end of the project Spanish Co-ops got in contact with [MAIL project's](#) members (Identifying Marginal Lands in Europe and strengthening their contribution potentialities in a CO₂ sequestration strategy). As a result of this collaboration, Wageningen University staff presented its mapping work on European marginal lands (performed within the MAGIC project) at MAIL's final event. In addition, MAIL's partners were also invited to MAGIC's final event, sharing a specific item of this collaboration [over their own website](#). The coordinator of the MAGIC project (CRES) also had the chance to share MAGIC's final outcomes at this event.

Other relevant interactions within MAGIC project framework with the EIP-AGRI and the Operational Groups can be further consulted over D8.5.

5 Conclusions

MAGIC project, through Spanish Co-ops membership at COPA-COGECA's, shared and presented the MAGIC project outcomes to near 150 members of sixteen different COPA-COGECA's WGs. In this sense, several presentations were performed by different MAGIC partners at various stages of MAGIC project life and in different modalities. Two of them could be held in presential format in Brussels and the rest were held in an online format due to COVID-19 pandemic restrictions.

Furthermore, MAGIC partners have been involved in several European events where farmers and cooperatives were present in order to enhance the outreach of MAGIC dissemination actions. In this sense, the projects were presented at several events from European Innovation Partnership for Agriculture Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI), European Network of Rural Development (ENRD) and European Commission (EC).

Moreover, COPA-COGECA's WPs members and EIP-AGRI staff were invited to MAGIC's final event, where they could be informed and had the chance to discuss directly about MAGIC's newest results with all the supporters.

6 References

Cooperativas Agro-alimentarias de España, 2020. *Webinar record: "Non-food Crops for European Marginal Lands"*.

[Seminario Web: Cultivos no-alimentarios para las zonas marginales europeas - YouTube](#)

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MAIL - Identifying Marginal Lands in Europe and strengthening their contribution potentialities in a CO2 sequestration strategy. *Website*

<https://marginallands.eu/>